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78. Finnish

Sources: Karlsson, F. : “Finnish – an essential grammar” (London, 1999)
Sulkala, H. & Karjalainen, M.: „Finnish“ (London, 1992)
All examples taken from this book exceptions are noted.

I. Segmental Properties

- form of basic stem (root, lexical form) often alters represented by different stems depending upon which ending it is followed by
- only /t, s, n, r, l/ can occur in final position in native words in standard Finnish
- /d, N/ cannot occur initially, exceptions in loanwords
- all 13 consonant phonemes can occur in the middle
- in general no word-initial consonant clusters, but it seems that clusters of a stop and a liquid become more and more acceptable – clusters are also to find in loanwords
- no word-final clusters except from loanwords, onomatopoeica, dialect forms
- clusters of two consonants later in words are possible but there are restrictions (p.371, Sulkala)
- clusters of three consonants common, particularly at the boundary between first and second syllable
- clusters of two consonants are numerous at the boundary between first and second syllable, restrictions p. 371 (Sulkala)
- except from /tk/ two different consonants with the same manner of articulation cannot be combined
- only in loanwords word-medial clusters of four consonants and in finnish slang
- often double plosive or plosive with /s/
- only /p, t, k, m, n, N, s, l, r/ can appear as geminates – syllable boundary is seldom a morpheme boundary
- geminated liquids always contain syllable boundary but not morpheme boundary – the same for nasals and fricatives
- all vowels are possible in word-initial and in word-final position
- sequences of vowels are possible up to three or four – as a result of consonant disappearing or in loanwords
- restriction on CC and VV combinations between and in first and second, second and third syllable but not in the latter syllables
- new consonant clusters which are impossible in lexical morphemes can appear at morpheme boundaries in compound words
- CC clusters which are normally impossible can also arise when adding clitic particles
- Restrictions about resonant consonants in syllable type CV(V)C (same consonant in the beginning and end) when first syllable (internal dissimilation)
- Restrictions in syllables:
/j/, /v/ are not freely followed by closest related vowels /i/, /u/ in first syllable
exceptions are loansrepresents tendency for dissimilation /d/, /j/ cannot appear at the end of a syllable after a vowel

-Lengthening: after certain grammatical forms the initial consonant of the following word or particle lengthens; ex.: mene pois [meneppois] ‘go away’

Vowel harmony:

Back / front, roundness, openness

Vowel of stem determines which ending is chosen

Some recent words of foreign origin which contain conflicting combinations of harmony

vowels fluctuate in ending selection;

ex.: amatööri – amatööri-

na ~ amatööri-nä ‘as an amateur’

Concern all vowels in a word form

○Internal harmony of morphemes concern both free and bound morphemes

○/i/, /e/ neutral in internal harmony

cross-morpheme vowel harmony operates linear – vowels of suffixes determined by the last

non- neutral vowel of the root or stem

if only /i/, /e/ occur : suffixes usually fronted

many loans without internal harmony but maintain suffix harmony

vowel harmony binds together the vowels of a word form and also functions as a boundary signal

compound word: vowel harmony affects each lexical component separately; e.x.: hätäapu ‘relief’

-sound alternation: consonant gradation /p, t, k/:

○adding of endings triggers sound alternations

○affect long, short stops of /p, t, k /

○quantitative consonant gradation : pp, tt, kk p, t, k

○short consonant alternates with other consonants however /k/ may sometimes be dropped = qualitative consonant gradation

○in polysyllabic stems long and short /p, t, k/ are subject to consonant gradation if they are followed by an ending which consists of only one consonant or begins with two consonants and also on condition that between /p, t, k/ and the ending there is only a short vowel or a diphthong (not consonants or a syllable boundary) and that the ending causing consonant gradation is usually the case ending in nominals and the personal ending in verbs;

ex.: katto > katon ‘roof > on the roof’

alternation only in verbs semantically, lexically governed

in three syllable nominals where there is a syllable boundary between the two final vowels in the basic form there is no consonant gradation ; ex.: keittiö > keittiön

‘kitchen > kitchen.gen.sg

many loanwords and proper names do not have consonant gradation

-sound alternation: vowel changes before –i-endings:

○certain endings beginning with –I

○long vowels shorten ; ex.: pu: > pu-ita ‘trees (partitive)’

○first vowel of diphthong dropped ; ex. : tie > teillä ‘on the roads’

○/i/ dropped in diphthongs ending in –I

○short /e/ dropped

○short –i changes to /e/ or is dropped

/ä/ is dropped almost always

/a/ remains, changes or is dropped (details p. 41 in Karlsson (1990)

-word-finally /n/ is partly assimilated according to the consonant in the beginning of the succeeding word ;ex.: menen pihalle > menem pihalle ‘I am going into the yard’

-earlier /k/, /h/ as word-final consonants used as

a relic: glottal stop in certain sandhi positions

phonetic marker of word boundary with no correspondence in writing system

when ? is followed by word-initial consonant : gemination of that consonant ; ex.: tullet
tQllep puolellek katua (written: tule tälle puolelle katua) ‘come to this side of the street’

when ? is followed by a vowel, a true ? may be pronounced; ex.: en
halua? ?olla? ?ulkona (written: en halua olla ulkona) ‘I don’t want to be outside’

-Assimilation:

Consonant assimilation: initial /t/ of first infinitive [tA] and second infinitive [te], tA-passive assimilate to a preceding dental resonant /l, r, n/ if the /e/ of the stem has disappeared in connection with stem formation; e.x.: ajattel ‘think’ ajatella (1inf),

ajattellaan (p-pass)

oInitial /n/ of the active potential mood /ne/ and the second participle active form /nUt/ assimilate to the preceding /l, r, s/ when the /e/ after the dental has disappeared in connection with stem formation

Final /t/ of stem is assimilated to the initial /n/ of the potential and second participle active
Assimilation also in connection with consonant gradation: suffix causes gradation while it closes the syllable; ex.: kampa ‘comb’ > kamman ‘comb-gen’

Partial assimilation: first vowel of disyllabic word is either /i, e, a/ and the second is /a/ /a/ becomes /o/ before the /i/ of plural or imperfect tense morphemes;

ex.: pila ‘joke’ > piloissa ‘joke-pl’

-Dissimilation:

oIn some cases (p.389, Sulkala), but no general rule

o/i/ > /e/ in stems ending in /i/ before the /i/ of the plural and superlative

-Metathesis:

oSome kinds as relics

oEx.: parhaan ‘good-sup-gen’ > parahiksi ‘good-sup-tra’

-coalescence: weakening of a geminate in connection with consonant gradation can be locked on as shortening or coalescence

Deletion:

oSome dases in connection with consonant gradation

oOne consonant dropped to avoid stem-final consonants

oDisyllabic stems ending in –a in which first vowel is /u/ or /o/ loose /a/ before plural and imperfect marker

oPolysyllabic stems lose final /a/ before imperfect marker /i/

oLoss of final /a/ in superlative

oLoss of final /Q/ before plural, imperfect, superlative (if disyllabic) marker

Loss of final /a/ in native polysyllabic nouns before plural marker /i/

/A/ must follow /m,v/

/jA/ must follow diphthong /Oi/ or a simple vowel but not /i/

dropping of /e/ in stems before /i/

dropping of final /i/ of verb stem before imperfect or conditional marker

o dropping of final /i/ in sequences Vi before suffixes beginning with /i/

o dropping of final vowel in sequences VV before plural, imperfect, conditional, superlative marker

dropping of /e/ after dentals in first and second infinitives passive, second participle active,

imperative, potential

polysyllabic verb stems ending in –tse loose –se in imperative

-insertion of /t/ in some cases in nom.sg and partitive.sg;

ex.: oluen ‘beer-gen’ > olut ‘beer’ olutta ‘beer-gen’

-onomatopoeic verbs and nouns, interjections do not always follow the typical phonotactics of Finnish:

○final consonant clusters or /h/ or /m/

rule of syllabification:

○syllable boundary before every sequence of a single consonant followed by a vowel

○also a boundary between vowels that do not form a diphthong ; ex.: no-pe-a ‘fast’

○basic rule: syllable boundary before each combination of CV

○in VVV sequences – syllable boundary between a double vowel or diphthong ending in /i/ and the single vowel or otherwise between the second and third vowel

○in VVVV boundary in the middle

○boundary between the elements of a compound word is also a syllable boundary

-in vowel sequences: vowels can either belong to the same or different syllables

-prototype lexical morpheme is of two syllables

-few monosyllabic words of CV – always lexical morphemes, ex.:

[me] ‘we’ [ja] ‘and’

-smallest possible syllable consists of one vowel

-structural possibilities for the basic syllable: (C)V(V/C)(C)

○at most two vowels always occurring consecutively

○only one C in beginning except in first syllable

○C-clusters in the end

○If two vowels no C-cluster in the end

-superheavy syllables: VVC, CVVC, VCC, VVCC

-marginal possibilities included (loanwords, slang): (C)(C)V(V/C)(C)(C)

-diphthong by themselves do not form any other lexeme or word except from interjections

II. Prosodic Properties

-main stress is always on the first syllable of the word

-secondary stress on third, fifth, ... syllable

-if third syllable is short and fourth long – secondary stress can fall on the fourth, sixth, ... ; ex.:

[vástustamàttomille] ‘opposite-dat.-pl-all’

-second syllable normally unstressed also the last

-many monosyllabic words are unstressed in continuous speech

-long vowels elsewhere than in first syllable are pronounced without main stress; ex.: tálo:n ‘into the house’

-the same held for loans even when they are stressed differently in the original language

-length and stress are independent: long can be unstressed, short stressed, but in dialects:

tendency to strengthen a short stressed syllable by geminating the first C of the following syllable; ex.: sataa [sáttá:] ‘rain’

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stress without distinctive function

-compounds:

- primary on first syllable of first element
- strong secondary on first syllable of second element regardless of number of intervening syllables
- stress-caricaturing function in compound words with three or more elements
- ex.: ` secondary (´) weak secondary ´ primary
[váltios(´ae:)ntoeù:distus] ‘constitution reform’
[júhla:jùmálp(à)lvelus] ‘commemorative divine service’
- same rules in morphological processes regarding stress
- morphological processes often increase the number of syllables and then affect the frequency of secondary stress

III. Morpho-Syntax

- morphology: concatenative, non-flexive; fixed order of endings – suffixing in general
- different degree of fusion: morpheme for imperative either merges with personal endings so that become indistinguishable or is followed by personal endings that are specific to this mood
 - passive morpheme discontinuous: elements (t)ta and Vn being separated by the tense and mood markers
 - stems ending in –se : se > nen (change and insertion)
 - polysyllabic verb stems ending in –ne : ne > t (change and deletion)
 - nouns of quality ending in –te: te > s in nom.sg part.
 - Superlative forms -impA > -in in nom. and partitive sg.
 - Polysyllabic verb vowel stems end in –tse alter in the second participle active and potential mood tse > n

-reduplication:

- wide variety of ideophones are reduplication
- often adverb pairs in the instructive case
- initial consonant remains with change in the following vowel, mostly /i/, /u/ in first member, /a/ in the latter
- /a/ never in first syllable of initial member
- totally; ex.: hujan hajan ‘in disorderly haste’; muksin maksin ‘upside down’
- if initial consonant changes, quality of an even process is usually described
- continuous aspect can also be expressed by stem reduplication: finite verb is followed by its own fourth infinitive partitive with a possessive suffix; ex.: Marja juoksi juoksemistaan.

Marja run-imp-(3sg) run-4inf-par-3poss
Marja ran and ran.

-clitics and particles: (examples from Karlsson)

- conjunctions – some are combinations of the negation verb and a conjunction, so they inflect for person; ex.: etten = että en, ettet = että et ‘that’
-

connectives are usually free morphemes except for the formative –kä attached to the negation verb and in negative coordination

- five common enclitic particles appended after all other types of endings – always occur last

- adjective (derived) + pronoun: senhetkinen (it-gen-moment-D) ‘of that moment’
- adjective + particle with alliteration as their first part: ex.:
putipuhdas ‘spotlessly clean’
- adverb + adverb: yltähyllin (upper-abl-enough) ‘more than enough’

-post- and prepositions:

- appear in phrases with object either in genitive or in partitive
- possible to attach possessive-suffix to postposition
- postposition trigger mostly genitive, preposition partitive
- same word can be used as postposition or preposition
- most postpositions have case inflection which forms an incomplete paradigm
- postpositions mostly originate from nouns, adverbs, non-finite verb forms
- complement: noun, numeral, pronoun require to appear in a certain case
- more common : postpositions
- same function can be expressed by preposition, postposition or case inflection alone
- in coordinated structure pre/postposition left out before or after one argument; ex.: *Matin ja Mikon kanssa* ‘Matti-gen and Mikko-gen with’
- if personal pronoun is used with postposition: possessive suffix is usually added to the postposition, but it is also possible to omit
- some can also occur alone – function as adverbs
- post/prepositional phrase not usually split – but sometimes possible a construction as an echo-question in the spoken language;
 - ex.: *kenen sinä tulit mu*
who-gen you come-imp-2sg with-ess
‘With whom did you come?’
- adverbs can modify prepositions, especially intensifying adverbs;
 - ex.: *tyttö tuli aivan ilman kankiä*
girl come-imp-(3sg) quite without shoe-pl-par
‘The girl came entirely without shoes.’
- Possible: postpositional phrase modify the preposition or prepositional phrase: *rahan suhteen* *pain seiniä olevat asiat*
Money-gen relation-gen head-pl-ins wall-pl-part be-1ptc-pl matter-pl
‘Matters that are all awry with regard to money.’
- Adverbial clause cannot usually modify post/prepositions
- There are also postmodifiers common in prepositional phrases;
 - ex.: *ennen matkaa Lontooseen*
Before journey-par London-il
‘before her / his journey to London’
ennen Lontoon matkaa
before London-gen journey-par
- Postmodifiers of the noun are rare in postpositional phrases
- Question words may also belong to pre/postpositional phrase
- Post/prepositional phrases sometimes function as modifiers of an adverb
- Sometimes closely attached to an adverb seems that the phrase modify it – relation not very fixed, can be split;

ex.: Irmeli oli Mattin kansaa kahdestaan
 Irmeli be-imp-(3sg) Matti-gen with two-ela-3.poss
 ‘Irmeli was there with Matti alone.’

-incorporation:

- formerly of compound verbs
- some verbs may have compound verb attached
- commonly an adverb, noun, prefix, adjective – not appear as separate lexeme
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ex.: Alleviian kysymyksen tärkeyttä.
 Under-line-1sg question-gen importance-par
 ‘I underline the importance of the question.’
 Koeajoin auton.
 Test-drive-imp-1sg car-acc
 ‘I test-drove the car.’
 Mustamaalata
 Black-paint-1inf
 ‘slander’

○element attached usually appear as adverbial in clause if compound were split – alternative use

○numerous constructions in which a verb with relative neutral meaning is completed semantically by its object

○

-periphrastic morphology:

○auxiliary verbs (negation verb and olla ‘be’) are free morphemes – bound only in the sense that they don’t usually appear without the main verb

○passive: two possible forms, one of them periphrastic

▪third person singular of olla ‘be’ and past (second) participle passive; ex.: on laulettu ‘it has been sung’

▪negative forms: negation verb ei followed by the main verb without a personal ending in the present, in the past the main verb is the past participle passive

○perfect:

▪verb olla in the present tense + the main verb in the singular or plural form of the past participle according to the number of the subject

▪perfect can occur in the indicative, conditional, potential moods, but imperative has no temporal use

▪ex.: on matkustanut ‘has travelled’

○pluperfect:

▪olla in the past + past participle of the main verb

▪ex.: oli ollut ‘had been’

○imperfect:

▪rather uncommon periphrastic imperfect

▪indicative imperfect of olla + the first participle active of the main verb

▪usually replaced by a normal imperfect

▪ex.: oli saava ‘was going to get’

○future:

▪present tense form of olla and first participle active of the main verb, but somewhat archaic

▪ more common: tulla ‘come’ + third infinitive illative of main verb

▪ ex.: olen ostava ; tulen ostamaan ‘I am going to buy’

○ habitual aspect:

▪ often used periphrastic construction: (jollakin) on/oli tapana ‘is/was in the habit of’

▪ ex.: on tapana metsästää

be-1sg habit-ess hunt-1inf

‘is in the habit of hunting’

○ continuous aspect: look chapter ‘reduplication’

○ progressive aspect: olla + third infinitive inessive of main verb

▪ ex.: on kokemassa ‘has gone to inspect’

▪ also be expressed by olla + deverbal noun’

▪ ex.: olen menossa kauppaan

be-1sg go-D-ine shop-ill

‘I am going to the shop.’

○ Ingressive aspect: alkaa ‘begin’ + 1inf; ruveta ‘start’, herjetä ‘start’ + third infinitive illative

▪ Olla + third infinitive adessive with the possessive suffix or first infinitive indicates situation where an attempt at beginning failed

○ Terminative aspect:

▪ Expressed by verbs such as lopettaa ‘finish’, loppua ‘end’, lakata ‘stop’, herjetä ‘stop’

▪ Ex.: Lakkaa satamasta. Sade lakkaa/ loppuu.

Stop-(3sg) rain-3inf-ela rain stop-(3sg) / end-3sg

‘It is stopping raining. The rain will stop.’

○ Intentional: indicated by lexical verbs aikoa or taitaa ‘intend’

▪ Ex.: aion tulla huomenna.

Intend-1sg come-1inf tomorrow-ess

I intend to come tomorrow.

○ Debitive:

▪ Expressed by verb chain in which the modal verb express the obligation and its degree

▪ Verb denoting the action itself is in the first infinitive, subject is in the genitive

▪ Ex.: sinun on autettava.

You-gen must-3sg go-1inf

‘You must go.’

▪ Obligation is also expressed by verb olla followed by the first participle passive

▪ Ex.: Sinun on autettava.

You-gen be-(3sg) help-p-1ptc

‘You must help.’

▪ Joutua ‘have to’ + 3rd infinitive illative

▪ Ex.: Sinä joudut tulemaan.

You must-2sg come-3inf-ill

You have to come.

○ Potential:

▪ Using the verbs voida ‘can’, saattaa ‘may’, kyetä, pystyä ‘be able to’ mainly physical ability

▪ Ex.: Marja voi leipoa jo huomenna.

Marja can-(3sg) bake-1inf already tomorrow-ess

‘Marja may bake tomorrow.’

▪ Ability which is learnt: verbs osata ‘know how’, kyetä ‘be able’

Ex.: Marja osaa lukea.

Marja can-(3sg) read-1inf
'Marja can read.'

○Assertion:

▪Expressed also by verbs pitää/ kuuluu

▪Ex.: Hän kuuluu tulevan.

s/he hear-D-3sg come-1ptc-acc
'It is said that s/he will come.'